

SOME THOUGHTS ON VICTIMOLOGICAL PREVENTION OF FRAUD BY THE PREVENTION INSPECTOR

Khidirov Furkat Shukrullaevich

Senior lecturer of the Department of Professional Special Sciences at
the Institute for Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of
the Republic of Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14202115>

Abstract: The article outlines the fundamentals and concepts of organizing victimological prevention of fraud by the inspector. Additionally, the author clarifies the concept of fraud victimization, the classification of specific objects of victimological crime prevention in implementing early victimological crime prevention measures, as well as their distinguishing features.

Keywords: victim, fraud, victimization, offense, prevention, victimological prevention.

Today, the increase in crimes of fraud, deception, and abuse of trust, as well as combating these types of crimes and offenses, is one of the main tasks of internal affairs bodies. Therefore, before analyzing the concepts related to this topic, we first need to understand what fraud is, or how to define this concept. Thus, fraud is categorized as a crime in the economic sphere, and Article 168 of the Criminal Code provides a definition for this crime.

According to it, fraud is the acquisition of someone else's property or the right to someone else's property through deception, trickery, or abuse of trust. Thus, any sane person who has reached the age of 16 who acquires another person's property or right to property for free using the two aforementioned methods may be prosecuted by law enforcement agencies as a person who has committed fraud. In this case, the amount of damage that serves as the basis for initiating a criminal case must exceed a small amount, which is 30 times the minimum monthly wage.

Today, this amount is 5,167,200 soums. If an individual has been victimized by a fraudster, according to criminal legislation, the amount of misappropriated property is not significant for initiating a criminal case. From a criminal law perspective, the legal assessment of this crime is primarily a matter of public concern. People are easily falling for the words of swindlers and being deceived. Therefore, let's present some thoughts on the causes of this type of crime, as well as who the main victims of this crime are and how to prevent them.

To enhance the effectiveness of internal affairs bodies directly implementing and participating in victimological crime prevention measures, it is necessary that their activities be directed towards specific targets. When studying the activities of the prevention inspector in organizing victimological prevention of fraud, it is important, first and foremost, to approach the concept of the victim from a victimological perspective as an object of victimological crime prevention. Therefore, a victim can be recognized not only as a person officially identified as a victim of a crime or an administrative offense but also as a person who has not yet become a victim but is at real risk due to antisocial behavior or illegal acts, regardless of whether an official of the competent authority formally recognizes them as a victim. As mentioned above, while the concept of victim in the direct implementation of

victimological prevention measures is interpreted relatively broadly in theory, the scope of the concepts of victim and victim of offense (criminal and administrative) used in the field of law and practice is limited, and they are interrelated. According to the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a person is recognized as a victim if there is evidence to believe that a crime or a socially dangerous act committed by an insane person caused moral, physical, or property damage to that person. The investigator, prosecutor issues a decision, and the court renders a ruling on the recognition of the victim" (Article 54 of the Criminal Procedure Code). When developing this definition, the legislator did not take into account the requirements of Part 2 of Article 14 of the Criminal Code, nor did it consider the latency of crimes and their victims when examining them from a victimological perspective.

In our view, there is a need to further improve the definition of the concept of victim of an offense provided for in Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses." Because this concept refers to a person who has suffered from an offense as a result of physical, moral or property damage, and somewhat limits the circle of victims. It is also possible to find that the objects of victimological crime prevention are interpreted differently in the eyes of different lawyers.

For example, E.Yu. Moshitskaya's research presents potential and victimized victims as objects of victimological prevention.[1] The study also emphasizes that the circle of individuals carrying out preventive measures depends on the types of prevention. For example, victimological prevention is implemented in relation to individuals with a high risk of becoming victims of trafficking.[2] In this case, the researcher took an individual approach to expressing his opinion. However, a group of researchers acknowledged that the object of victimological prevention is not limited to victims, but includes individuals with a high risk of becoming victims of human trafficking, as well as the factors and causes that cause victims of human trafficking. After all, the less people in society are prone to be victims of offenses, as well as the lower their level of victimization, the more effective it can be in combating crime.[4] It is also emphasized that not all of those listed in legal literature as objects of victimological crime prevention by internal affairs bodies can be accepted as objects of this activity. Because the study of the concept of victimization, the types, methods, forms, measures, directions, and legal foundations of victimological prevention is an object of science and research, not of this activity.

Victimological crime prevention measures used by internal affairs bodies are aimed, firstly, at factors that shape a propensity to be victimized by offenses and require victimhood, secondly, at those with a high probability of being victimized by offenses, and thirdly, at victims of offenses.

Therefore, the activity of organizing victimological prevention of fraud by a prevention inspector can be understood as social relations that shape a predisposition (high probability) to be victimized by offenses within the framework of crime prevention measures, factors requiring victimization, and ensuring the presence of victims in society.

The following can be cited as the main reasons for the emergence of this type of fraudulent crimes; the lack of awareness of the essence of the crime, the interest of young people and minors in various games (online gambling, various types of paid games) and their insufficient control by family members, the credibility of victims. Based on the above analysis and the results of the conducted research, the classification of objects of victimological crime

prevention activities of internal affairs bodies made it possible to conditionally divide them into three groups.

The first group includes factors that shape victimization (features that determine the likelihood of being victimized by offenses) in the population, its individual groups, and specific individuals.

The second group includes categories of the population, groups, and individuals with a high probability of becoming victims of a crime and who in certain situations may become victims. (for example, depending on their physical and physiological condition: children, elderly people, women, people with disabilities, people with physical and (or) mental disabilities, etc.).

The third group includes victims of a crime. victims of a crime (persons whose primary victim suffered physical, material, and moral harm as a result of the commission of a crime, as well as a person whose secondary victim suffered moral harm as a result of the commission of a crime against a close relative, legal representation, or patronage.

In cooperation with the bodies carrying out the prevention of crimes and offenses and the relevant departments involved in it, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at providing legal, social, psychological, medical, pedagogical and other types of assistance, as well as instilling in them accepted norms and rules of conduct in society.

In conclusion, it is advisable for the above-mentioned prevention inspector to implement victimological prevention measures for fraud in conjunction with general, special, and individual prevention measures

References:

1. Мошицкая Е.Ю. Виктимологическая характеристика сексуального насилия несовершеннолетних (по материалам Иркутской области) /Афтреф. дисс.И.: 2004. С.19.
2. Fazilov I.Yu., Criminal Law and Criminological Problems of Combating Trafficking in Persons: Monograph. -Т.: Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2016. - Б. 181
3. Rivman D.V. Criminal victimology. СПб.: Питер, 2002. С. 13; Задорожный В.И. Виктимологическая профилактика преступлений: организационно-управленческий и правовой аспект: монография. М.: Академия управления МВД России, 2005. С. 62-69. Sidorenko E.L. Negative behavior of the victim and criminal law. SPb.: Legal Center Press, 2003. С. 33.
4. Nadtoka S.V. Victimological aspects of prevention of violent crimes. Abstract. Diss... канд. юрид. наук. - М., 1999 (Nadtoka S.V. Victimological aspects of prevention of violent crimes. Abstract. Diss.... Cand. the faculty of law sciences. - Тошкент, 2020.
5. Khojakulov S.B., Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in the Prevention of Offenses // Textbook. - Тошкент, 2017. P.107-108